

***N*-Aryl-*N'*-2-benzothiazolyguanidines. Part I**

P. N. Bhargava and K. Syamala Devi

Several *N*-aryl-*N'*-2-benzothiazolyguanidines have been prepared and tested for their antibacterial activity.

Several types of biguanides have been obtained by many workers and their antibacterial and antimalarial activities have been determined. The authors are therefore interested in the preparation of diarylguanidines in which one aryl group is benzothiazolyl and another is a substituted phenyl group. Synthesis of some of these compounds is reported in the present communication. 2-Aminobenzothiazole was condensed with appropriate aryl isothiocyanates and the resulting thiocarbamides were desulphurised with lead oxide in ethanolic ammonia; the guanidines, so obtained, were converted into the corresponding hydrochlorides.

Antibacterial activities of these compounds were tested against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. It has been observed that these compounds are more active to gram-positive bacteria than to gram-negative ones.

EXPERIMENTAL

Aryl Isothiocyanates.—Phenyl, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-methyl-, *p*-chloro-, *p*-bromo-, *p*-methoxy-, *p*-ethoxy-phenyl, and benzyl isothiocyanates were prepared according to the method described by Vogel¹.

N-Aryl-*N'*-2-benzothiazolyl Thiocarbamides

Equimolecular quantities of 2-aminobenzothiazole and appropriate isothiocyanates were refluxed in dry benzene for 3 to 6 hours. The resulting product was washed with ether and HCl (dil.) to remove the unchanged isothiocyanates and 2-aminobenzothiazole. The thiocarbamides were crystallised from ethanol or glacial acetic acid. The results and analytical data are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Isothiocyanates.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.		% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	Phenyl	206°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂	14.70	14.73	22.47	22.46
2	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	201°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	14.03	14.05	21.46	21.40
3	<i>m</i> -Methyl "	190°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	14.02	14.05	21.51	21.40
4	<i>p</i> -Methyl "	202°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	14.10	14.05	21.49	21.40
5	<i>p</i> -Chloro "	218°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₃ ClS ₂	13.12	13.14	20.32	20.03
6	<i>p</i> -Bromo "	218°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₃ BrS ₂	11.48	11.53	17.56	17.54
7	<i>p</i> -Methoxy "	208°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ON ₃ S ₂	13.29	13.33	20.40	20.33
8	<i>p</i> -Ethoxy "	200°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ ON ₃ S ₂	12.76	12.76	19.50	19.45
9	Benzyl	182°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	14.01	14.05	22.41	21.40

N-Aryl-N'-2-benzothiazolylguanidines

N-Phenyl-N'-2-benzothiazolyl thiocarbamide(3 g.), yellow lead oxide (4 g.), and strong ethanolic ammonia (20 ml) were heated in a sealed tube on a water bath for 3 to 4 hours. Lead sulphide was filtered and N-phenyl-N'-2-benzothiazolylguanidine was obtained from the filtrate. It was recrystallised from ethanol in white plates, m.p. 152°, yield 2 g. (Found: N, 20.82; S, 12.01. C₁₄H₁₂N₄S requires N, 20.84; S, 11.94%). The analytical data are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

No.	Aryl group.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.		% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	Phenyl	152°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₄ S	20.82	20.89	12.01	11.94
2	o-Methylphenyl	172°	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₄ S	19.80	19.86	11.32	11.34
3	m-Methyl "	134°	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₄ S	19.86	19.86	11.50	11.34
4	p-Methyl "	181°	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₄ S	19.81	19.86	11.41	11.34
5	p-Chloro "	125°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₄ ClS	18.42	18.51	10.82	10.56
6	p-Bromo "	156°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₄ BrS	16.12	16.09	9.20	9.19
7	p-Methoxy "	138°	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ ON ₄ S	18.70	18.79	10.71	10.74
8	p-Ethoxy "	143°	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ON ₄ S	17.89	17.95	10.51	10.25
9	Benzyl	118°	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₄ S	19.84	19.86	11.50	11.34

Hydrochlorides of N-Aryl-N'-2-benzothiazolylguanidines

To N-phenyl-N'-2-benzothiazolylguanidine, dissolved in dry ether, dry HCl gas was passed. The white precipitate, so obtained, was filtered, dried, and crystallised from absolute ethanol and HCl mixture; m.p. 190°. (Found: N, 18.38; S, 10.52. C₁₄H₁₃N₄S.HCl requires N, 18.40, S, 10.51%). The results are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

No.	Aryl group.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.		% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	Phenyl	190°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₄ ClS	18.38	18.40	10.52	10.51
2	o-Methylphenyl	218°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₄ ClS	17.52	17.58	10.08	10.05
3	m-Methyl "	145°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₄ ClS	17.50	17.58	10.12	10.05
4	p-Methyl "	220°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₄ ClS	17.51	17.58	10.11	10.05
5	p-Chloro "	200°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₄ Cl ₂ S	16.48	16.53	9.48	9.44
6	p-Bromo "	220°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₄ BrClS	14.50	14.56	8.34	8.32
7	p-Methoxy "	228°	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ ON ₄ ClS	16.70	16.74	9.61	9.56
8	p-Ethoxy "	130°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ ON ₄ ClS	16.01	16.07	9.20	9.18
9	Benzyl "	236°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₄ ClS	17.54	17.58	10.11	10.06

Antibacterial Activity

The hydrochlorides of the compounds mentioned above were tested for their antibacterial activity according to the procedure described by Mackie and Macartney*. The test organisms were *Staphylococcus aureus* and *E. coli*. The maximum effective dilutions are recorded for each compound in Table IV.

3, "An Introduction to Practical Bacteriology" 4th ed., pp. 241-242.

TABLE IV

Maximum effective dilution.

No.	Aryl group.	<i>E. coli.</i>	<i>S. aureus.</i>
1	Phenyl	1 : 250	1 : 1000
2	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	1 : 250	1 : 1000
3	<i>m</i> -Methyl ..	1 : 250	1 : 1500
4	<i>p</i> -Methyl ..	1 : 500	1 : 2000
5	<i>p</i> -Chloro ..	1 : 500	1 : 2000
6	<i>p</i> -Bromo ..	1 : 500	1 : 2000
7	<i>p</i> -Methoxy ..	1 : 250	1 : 1500
8	<i>p</i> -Ethoxy ..	1 : 500	1 : 1000
9	Benzyl	1 : 250	1 : 1000

Thanks are due to the authorities of the Banaras Hindu University for providing necessary facilities and to Dr. Phulgan Ram, Ph.D., for helping in testing the antibacterial activity of the compounds.

ORGANIC SECTION,
CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
BANARAS HINDU UNIVERSITY,
VARANASI.

Received September 20, 1962.